

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Development of alcoholic fermented beverages from coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L.)

Desarrollo de bebidas fermentadas alcohólicas a partir de agua de coco (*Cocos nucifera* L.)

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Abstract In Cuba, coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) production represents a key sector in the economy of certain regions, with the municipality of Baracoa being the largest national producer, primarily aimed at oil extraction. However, in recent years, a significant decline in dry coconut production has been observed, decreasing from 21,298 tons in the 1980s to just 7,499.9 tons in 2011. The objective of this study was to develop two alcoholic fermented beverages based on coconut water as a strategy to diversify production and mitigate the decrease in dry coconut harvest. Two alcoholic fermented beverages were prepared with an initial soluble solids content of 15 and 22%, respectively. Physical, chemical, microbiological, and sensory analyses were performed on the final product, finding that both alcoholic fermented beverages met the microbiological requirements established for this type of food. Variant 1 showed low acceptance among consumers, while variant 2 was well-accepted and considered satisfactory for consumption, presenting a pleasant appearance. Significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were found between both treatments in the physical and chemical parameters. Variant 2 met the established requirements for a wine-type alcoholic fermented beverage, representing an option for the industrialization and commercialization of coconut water.

Keywords coconut water, alcoholic fermentation, beverage production, industrialization, sensory analysis.

Resumen En Cuba, la producción de coco (*Cocos nucifera* L.) representa un sector clave en la economía de ciertos territorios, siendo el municipio de Baracoa, el mayor productor nacional, destinado principalmente a la obtención de aceite. Sin embargo, en los últimos años, se observó una notable disminución en la producción de coco seco, que pasó de 21,298 t en la década de los ochenta a solo 7,499.9 t en 2011. El objetivo de este estudio fue desarrollar dos bebidas fermentadas alcohólicas a base de agua de coco como una estrategia para diversificar la producción y mitigar la disminución en la cosecha de coco seco. Se elaboraron dos bebidas fermentadas alcohólicas con un contenido inicial de sólidos solubles de 15 y 22 %, respectivamente. Se realizaron análisis físicos, químicos, microbiológicos y sensoriales al producto final, encontrando que ambas bebidas fermentadas alcohólicas cumplían con los requisitos microbiológicos establecidos para este tipo de alimento. La variante 1 mostró una baja aceptación entre los consumidores, mientras que la variante 2 fue bien aceptada y se consideró satisfactoria para el consumo, presentando una apariencia agradable. Se encontraron diferencias significativas ($p \leq 0.05$) entre ambos tratamientos en los parámetros físicos y químicos. La variante 2 cumplió con los requisitos establecidos para una bebida fermentada alcohólica tipo vino, representando una opción para la industrialización y comercialización del agua de coco.

Palabras clave agua de coco, fermentación alcohólica, producción de bebidas, industrialización, análisis sensorial.

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Introduction

The coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera* L.) is the most widely cultivated tree crop in the world and has been closely linked to the development of various cultures. It is used as a source of food, drink, oil, fiber, fuel, wood, and other products (Alvarado et al., 2013). Currently, it is considered one of the most profitable perennial crops globally due to the high demand for its products and their diverse uses (Nogueira, 2000).

In Cuba, coconut cultivation is distributed across several regions of the country, with the largest areas of cultivation primarily located in Baracoa, Guantánamo province, in the municipalities of Niquero and Pilon in Granma province, as well as in several municipalities in Holguín, Pinar del Río, and Sancti Spiritus. This crop is a tradition and holds great economic importance in the municipality of Baracoa, where the largest volume of the national coconut production is concentrated (Alvarado & Blanco, 2021). It is mainly found as a monoculture, with small intercropping systems and integrated with livestock in some plantations (Alvarado et al., 2013).

In recent years, dried coconut production has decreased from 21,298 tons in the 1980s to 7,499.9 tons in 2011 (Alvarado et al., 2013). Due to deficiencies in commercialization, part of the production is used as animal feed (Alvarado et al., 2013), which represents an underutilization given the wide industrialization and diversification potential of coconut by-products (Nogueira, 2000).

This situation has prompted interest in the production of fermented alcoholic beverages to diversify output, thus increasing farmers' income and enhancing the profitability of coconut plantations. These products open up a new market, increasing the economic benefits for producers. Moreover, wine production ensures the creation of a stable and long-lasting product at room temperature (Díaz, 2016). In this context, the objective of this study was to develop two fermented alcoholic beverages based on coconut water as a strategy to diversify production and mitigate the decline in dried coconut harvests.

Materials and methods

Coconuts (*C. nucifera* L.) of the Criolla variety were collected from the Ronera Santa Cruz del Norte for the production of fermented alcoholic beverages. The pH (AOAC, 943.02) and the dissolved solids content in the coconut water were measured to adjust the initial conditions of the musts. Fermentation was carried out at two initial concentrations of soluble solids, 15 and 22 °Brix, with visual monitoring of fermentation duration and alcohol content (°GL, Gay Lussac degrees).

The musts were inoculated with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and fermented in 5 L glass fermenters without temperature control, protected from light. After fermentation, the musts were racked and clarified by sedimentation for 30 days. They were then filtered using a vacuum pump and a cellulose plate. The filtered fermented alcoholic beverages were adjusted to 15% alcohol to improve stability and prevent microbial contamination, bottled, and stored for 30 days.

Physicochemical analyses of the final products were conducted in triplicate, including pH, titratable acidity (AOAC 942.15, 2005), alcohol content (AOAC, 957.03, 2005), soluble solids content (AOAC 932.12, 2005), absorbance, and transmittance at three wavelengths (420, 520, and 620 nm). Additionally, mesophilic aerobic microorganism counts (NTC 404, 2007) and mold and yeast counts (NTC 404, 2007) were performed on the fermented alcoholic beverages to confirm the effectiveness of the alcohol adjustment for microbiological stabilization.

Eighty consumers using a 7-point hedonic scale, with additional questions to identify factors of acceptance or rejection, evaluated the fermented alcoholic beverages sensorially. The results were analyzed through ANOVA and LSD mean comparison using Statgraphics Centurion XV software, to identify significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in sensory quality based on the initial concentrations of soluble solids.

Results and discussion

The analysis of coconut water revealed a soluble solids content of 5.3 °Brix and a pH of 5.7, values that are inadequate for an optimal wine fermentation process. The need for chaptalization and must acidification is an important finding, as these steps are essential to optimize yeast growth, as discussed in previous studies (Ashurst & Arthey, 2001; Camargo et al., 2015). Table 1 presents the averages of the analyses conducted on the replicas.

This nutrient deficiency, such as vitamins, can compromise the proper development of the yeasts, which aligns with findings from other researchers who claim that coconut water may not provide enough nutrients for effective fermentation (Dewanto et al., 2015).

The results indicate that both alcoholic fermented beverages should be classified as sweet wines, supported by the observation that the acidity of alcoholic fermented beverage 1 (4.0 ± 0.1) was lower than the values reported by Paup et al. (2022) for white grape wines, which have a higher average acidity. On the other hand, the total acidity results from Scheihing (2005), ranging from 1.87 to 2.66 g/L for cranberry wines, align with the values obtained in alcoholic fermented beverage 2.

Table 1. Physical and chemical analysis of alcoholic fermented beverages from coconut water

Parameter	Fermented alcoholic beverage 1	Fermented alcoholic beverage 2
Total acidity (g/L)	3.12 (0.02) a	2.58 (0.01) a
Alcohol content at the end of fermentation (%)	6.14 (0.07) b	8.23 (0.06) a
pH	3.02 (0.01) a	3.47 (0.02) a
Soluble solids content	6.0 (0.2) b	10.0 (0.2) a
Absorbance at 420 nm	0.086 (0.01) b	0.222 (0.1) a
Absorbance at 520 nm	0.027 (0.01) b	0.086 (0.01) a
Absorbance at 620 nm	0.006 (0.001) b	0.033 (0.01) a
Transmittance at 420 nm (%)	82.0 (1) a	60.0 (0.1) b
Transmittance at 520 nm (%)	93.9 (0.3) a	82.1 (0.1) b
Transmittance at 620 nm (%)	98.6 (0.5) a	92.7 (0.3) b

Mean (standard deviation); n = 3.

Different letters for the same parameter indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$).

Regarding pH, the values obtained were consistent with those reported in the literature. Paup et al. (2022) found an average pH of 3.25 for white grape wines, while Mendes-Ferreira et al. (2019) reported a range of 3.0 to 3.26 for cranberry wines. This suggests that the pH of the coconut water fermented beverages is within the expected range for fermented products, although acidification remains a critical point.

The low alcohol percentages at the end of fermentation were due to the limited consumption of sugars, which restricted the alcoholic potential. This phenomenon is consistent with other studies that have documented the relationship between initial sugar concentration and final alcohol content in wines (Samphao et al., 2018). The incomplete fermentation observed in alcoholic fermented beverage 2 has also been reported in other works, where sweet wines requiring additional alcohol adjustments to improve stability have been found (Ruiz-Bejarano et al., 2020).

Absorbance and transmittance values indicated that fermented beverage 2 had a darker color, with higher absorbance at 420 nm (0.222 vs. 0.086), suggesting a greater yellow color intensity. This behavior is related to the concentration of coloring compounds during fermentation, as noted by researchers studying the influence of different substrates on pigment production in wines (Waterhouse et al., 2016).

The sensory acceptance of the fermented beverages showed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$). Alcoholic fermented beverage 1 had an average of 3.76, indicating moderate rejection, while beverage 2 reached an average of 5.89, indicating acceptance. These findings reflect the importance of aroma and flavor in product acceptance, aligning with pre-

vious studies that highlight the role of sensory profiles in consumer preference (Barbe et al., 2021).

Finally, the counts of aerobic mesophilic microorganisms, molds, and yeasts below 101 CFU/mL in all batches emphasize the effectiveness of the processing techniques used, such as filtration and good hygienic practices. This aligns with the results of recent studies that emphasize the importance of microbiological control measures in the production of fermented beverages (Sharma et al., 2020).

Conclusions

The initial soluble solids and pH values in the coconut water were inadequate for proper fermentation, making it necessary to adjust both sugar and acidity levels. The physical and chemical analyses revealed significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the two products. These differences were also reflected in sensory attributes and consumer acceptance. The adjustment of the alcohol content to 15% ensured microbiological stability, with microorganism counts below acceptable limits. Significant differences in consumer perception were observed, with higher acceptance for fermented alcoholic beverage 2, characterized by its coconut aroma, balanced flavor, and attractive color. The production of fermented alcoholic beverages from coconut water presents interesting potential but requires adjustments in must conditions and the fermentation process to improve both the physical and chemical characteristics as well as the sensory acceptance of the final product.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

Orlando Vargas and Evelyn A. Rivera: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, validation, visualization, drafting the original manuscript and writing, review, and editing.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies to improve the readability and clarity of the article.

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